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THE IMPACT OF ELECTRONIC PROMOTION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOUNTAIN TOURISM - CASE STUDY MOUNTAIN REGIONS IN KOSOVO

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyze the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism (case study mountain regions in Kosovo). Genuine electronic promotion is one of the main causes that affects the flow of tourists, therefore our main goal is to see the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism where we have the Regions of Kosovo as a case study. 100 respondents participated in this study in the 4 mountainous tourist regions in Kosovo, the mountains of Sharri, in Bajgora, in the mountains of Nemuna and in the mountains of Karadak. Since we do not have accurate statistics for the number of tourists in these mountain tourist places, we surveyed 25 tourists from each of these tourist places. For the methodology of this study, the qualitative (quantitative) method was used. In this study, a measuring instrument with 20 closed-type questions was used, which is compatible with the research questions and the objectives of this study. The findings of this study have shown that in the mountains of Sharr, the minimum rating of the respondents is 2, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.16 and the standard deviation is 0.78. In the mountains of Rugova, the minimum rating of the respondents is 1, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.56 and the standard deviation is 0.80, we also see that 62% of the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo is explained by electronic promotion.

KEY WORDS: electronic promotion, mountain tourism, mountain regions, impact.

INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technologies (ICT), as well as geospatial technologies (GT), have emerged as important tools to support the development of sustainable tourism, especially in natural regions. Also, tourists are increasingly interested in receiving information electronically about geographic spaces to maximize their experiences in national parks. Even during travel planning, searching for information online can be considered an essential component of the travel experience. Similarly, nature-based destinations can benefit from technology adoption (Schnitzer, 2018).

With the use of different technologies, the decision-making process to visit a destination has become dependent on the quality of information and ICT. For example, websites, social media, sharing sites, mobile applications, and GT, such as global positioning system (GPS) and geographic information system (GIS), can assist in this process. Then, all the relevant data must be accessed online and on the official websites of the travel destinations (Pilving & Suskevics, 2019).

Sustainable economic development, ecological sustainability, electronic promotion, and environmental protection are essential for the development of mountain tourism and its potential benefits to the local population, such as improvements in access and communication infrastructure and the creation of jobs and businesses. Information and communication technologies (ICT) and geospatial technologies (GT) provide support to manage protected areas, such as national parks, while increasing electronic promotion, promoting sustainable development of tourism activities in pioneer national parks (Tian & Ming, 2021).

Recently, mountain tourism has been seen to be safer than other forms of tourism because it has the potential to minimize the spread of COVID-19. The complex tourism interests, as well as the variety of natural and cultural resources in remote and often unexplored geographical environments, provide a refuge in which the impact of the pandemic is reduced compared to urban areas. Mountain tourism includes sociocultural tourist activities as well as climbing, hiking, adventure, cycling, hiking, touring, or other activities. As a result of this mountain tourism is searched online by tourists and has gradually become a favorite type of tourism for tourists (Thorn & Sterger, 2021).

The purpose and objectives of the research

Genuine electronic promotion is one of the main causes that affect the flow of tourists. Therefore, the main purpose of our study is to see the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism in the regions of Kosovo. To achieve this goal, we defined several study objectives:

1. To identify the most important mountain regions in Kosovo that have an impact on the development of mountain tourism. This will help us focus on key regions and understand their tourism potentials.
2. To analyze the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo. We will investigate how the electronic promotion of these regions affects the increase in the number of tourists and the development of tourist infrastructure.

Research questions and study hypotheses

Based on the objectives set for the research, the research questions that will be answered through this research are:

Q1. What are the most important mountain regions in Kosovo that have an impact on the development of tourism?

Q2. What impact does electronic promotion have on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo?

Research hypotheses

H1. The most important mountain regions in Kosovo, which have an impact on the development of tourism, are the Sharri Mountains and the Rugova Mountains.

H2. Electronic promotion has a positive impact on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The basics of the presentation of theories and the development of tourism

The evolutionary development of human history has passed through different phases and stages of the period of unorganized life for the birth of the need for

travel. Since that time, man has had the need to move and he has done this movement in different ways and for different motives.

One of the theories was given by Altier, according to his presentation, tourism is the best indicator between the past and modernity and antiquity, it also shows the past. Critics approach the connection between travel and the presentation of tourism, as an economic-social phenomenon, where its presentation is made by technical-technological, economic-social needs and the development of traffic and settlement infrastructure, as well as the increase of the standard in the strata social and people's needs for travel motives (Oglive, 2013).

Contemporary tourism differs from that of the past with the free time available and the free means, based on the motives to travel. Always moving in geographical spaces and enjoying different natural motifs and cultural heritage values. The presentation of tourist trips, according to the publications of the world organization, is divided into 5 periods: (Fetah & Millaku, 2011).

1. The early period - the first civilizations in Greece, Rome and Asia.
2. Middle period - from the V-XIV century, by pedestrians, and research trips.
3. The Renaissance period from the XIV-XVII century, educational trips called the Grand Tour.
4. The industrial revolution from 1750 to 1850, the development of cities and the steam engine.
5. Modern tourism, circulation development, spending people and mass tourism (Fetah & Millaku, 2011).

Mountain tourism

The arrival of visitors to the village for recreational reasons is called mountain tourism and is closely related to the interests of relaxing in nature and getting to know a culture and way of life up close. In general, guests who practice this type of tourist activity prefer to spend their holidays in nature and in an active way, such as mountain hiking, mountain biking, skiing, etc. They enjoy the hospitality of the mountain areas, but also the cleanliness, natural foods, and mountain scenery. For the inhabitants of mountainous areas, tourism has become a good economic opportunity, developing the activity where you live. Some areas in Kosovo are known, which previously had income only from agriculture and livestock, which now have satisfactory income from an additional activity such as tourism. Among the most sought-after businesses

in these mountainous areas, are the guesthouses that offer food and host local and foreign guests in their family accommodation structures, which in most cases are two to four rooms of the host's house that have been put available to visitors (Alzadeh & Isa, 2015).

Mountain tourism has a high potential to stimulate local economic growth and social change due to its complementarity with other economic activities, its contribution to GDP and the creation of new jobs, and its capacity to promote the distribution of timely demand (combating seasonality) and beyond. New and innovative products can transform mountain areas into attractive tourist destinations, especially for the shoulder season. Among the many possibilities are gastronomic tourism, community-based tourism, spiritual tourism, wellness tourism, mountain tourism, agritourism, and cultural tourism (Uysal & Noe, 2003).

The case studies presented in this publication highlight solutions being implemented or tested in mountain regions around the world. Many of these have involved rethinking tourism initiatives or creating new opportunities, and all aim to bring tangible benefits to local communities, helping to enhance the conservation of the unique mountain heritage (Ansoff, 2018).

Advantages of Mountain Tourism

Mountain tourism, especially involving people living in the countryside, creates new income opportunities. Visitors to these areas seek the authentic experience and not the luxury of large hotels, so this opportunity is achievable with very small investments by adapting your personal home into a guesthouse for visitors. Many mountainous areas in Kosovo are mostly abandoned by young people who move towards urban centers for a better life and greater economic opportunities. Meanwhile, mountain tourism creates an opportunity for the further emptying of these areas, but in many cases also the return of youth to the village, offering new employment opportunities for young people, who very quickly adapt to the new demands of tourism and technology that surrounds them. Traditional cooking, crafts, and customs are an integral part of the mountain experience for visitors, but with the abandonment of these areas, the villages risk the disappearance of these values. People who participate in this type of tourism are passionate about nature and sensitive to issues that harm it, so by their actions, they take care to set a good example of its preservation (Olivier, 2008).

Also, with the development of mountain tourism, which is impossible without a nature, the attention of institutions turns more towards these areas, preserving them to provide sustainable economic benefits for the area. Mountain tourism also contributes to the awareness of the residents of the area for the preservation of inalienable natural values as well as the provision of alternative income in order not to negatively affect nature. Sustainable development is one of the challenges of today, to achieve economic benefits ethically towards society and the environment, protecting natural resources from over-exploitation and destruction to have a continuity of income (Uncles & Hammond, 2003).

THE NATURAL RESOURCES OF KOSOVO

Kosovo, which is located in the center of the Balkan Peninsula, its territory with a very complex natural composition with hilly, hilly-mountainous, and plain areas, traversed by rivers, is very attractive for researchers and visitors. With its rare beauty, natural resources, and aesthetic values, as well as the biological diversity of plant and animal species, the territory of Kosovo is one of the most unique in the Balkan Peninsula and beyond (Sinclar, 2008).

In the publication "Natural Heritage Values of Kosovo" basic data on the most representative natural values of Kosovo, protected and proposed for protection, are presented. The protected values of nature include an area of 46,247.3 ha or 4.27% of the territory of Kosovo. Of them, a National Park, 11 Nature Reserves, 37 Natural Monuments and 2 Protected Landscapes. From the most representative nature values of Kosovo, we mention: Sharri Mountains National Park, Marble Cave in Gadime, Mirusha Canyon, Germia Park, Nerodime River Bifurcation, Rugova Gorge, etc (Bakiu, 2020).

The Kosovo Institute for Nature Protection, as a central institution for nature conservation, monitors the state of protected values and at the same time identifies the new natural values of particular importance. So far, about 200 sites have been identified, among which a National Park, several natural landscapes, and many natural monuments with a botanical and hydrological character. With the declaration of The Cursed Mountains as a second National Park and with the taking under protection of the proposed areas, the total area of the protected areas would increase significantly (about 10% of the territory of Kosovo) (Buhalis D. , 2017).

Some of the tourist places in Kosovo, Mountain Complexes: Sharri Mountains, The Cursed Mountains, where Brezovica and Rugova stand out as skiing and recreation centers, Maja e Luboteni, Maja e Gjeravica which is known as the highest peak in Kosovo that reaches a height of 2,656 meters, etc (Buhalis D. , 2017).

From a tourist point of view, Kosovo is divided into five tourist regions:

1. Central region of Pristina;
2. The tourist region of the Albanian Alps;
3. Sharri tourist region;
4. Anamorava tourist region;
5. Tourist region of Mitrovica.

Based on the studies so far in the Republic of Kosovo, there are very good conditions for the establishment of tourist centers for winter sports tourism. The tourist region of the Albanian Alps and the region of Sharr are two regions that have the best opportunities for the development of this type of tourism (Buhalis D. , 2017).

THE CONTRIBUTION OF ELECTRONIC MARKETING IN MOUNTAIN TOURISM

Marketing's contribution to mountain tourism is multidimensional, as it empowers organizations to improve their internal efficiency, develop their effectiveness in their communication with their external world, and create partnerships with collaborators and stakeholders (Wardell, 1998).

Marketing enables organizations to use the opportunities offered by the three approaches and create combinations of possible tools to facilitate communication and interaction with partners and stakeholders. They use the three main marketing accesses to carry out internal processes (intranet), to communicate with established external partners (extranet) and to interact with consumers and society in general (Internet). The information space between the accesses provides endless combinations for the development and distribution of products, as well as for the adaptation of procedures and business processes. Given the dynamic nature of the industry, as well as the rapid development of technological tools, organizations will need to continue to update their offerings, processes, and partnerships to continuously improve their competitiveness and keep abreast of developments (Bagaturi & Johnson, 2014).

Electronic promotion of the natural landscape, tourism in Kosovo

Nature with its preserved structures is an important factor for preserving the health of the population, because it makes possible the direct encounter of man with it, both physical and psychological renewal. Human is not satisfied with pure nature just by looking at it, but he develops an intense and active life, which directly affects the degree of its use. The growth of the world's population, the rate of technological and urban development, as well as the rise of the standard of living in the future, will create many free natural spaces (Morrison, Anderson, & Donald, 2002).

Spaces where tourism is developed are areas of tourist traffic, therefore they must be actively protected from human consequences. But even the tourists who have a physiognomy of nature must preserve it because they have temporarily abandoned their place of residence, due to the disruption of the natural balance (Gretzel, 2018).

The tourist propaganda of many countries of the world has created renewal programs for preserved natural environments, as an offer for local and foreign tourists in the world. The devaluation of nature is such a threat that a single country cannot oppose it but requires the joint work of many organizations and individuals. In the framework of the environmental impacts of tourism, two important problems should be taken into account:

Firstly, the connection of the tourist system with the ecological system: the tourist system can realize a structural development in close connection with the ecological one.

Secondly, the tourist system is in constant connection with the system of tourist resources, with the flows of tourists, goods, financial exchanges and information.

Tourism is a complete cultural phenomenon, which allows the exchange of knowledge and opens new worlds outside the pre-prepared schemes of the industrial age (Fielding & Pearce, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

Research methods

This study is based on self-report measures of participants through questionnaires. Data analysis will be done through descriptive data and linear regression, depending on the change being analyzed. The questionnaire was used to collect data from the sample to describe the attitudes, opinions, methods, and strategies or characteristics of the sample under consideration. This is a method that can be quickly implemented and administered by the researcher, has very limited or no impact on the participants, and allows the researcher to identify certain elements in specific groups.

Research techniques and instruments

We used the questionnaire as a research technique. In this study, we applied a closed-type questionnaire. The questionnaire contained the demographic data of the respondents and 20 questions with 5 rating scales which give us data on the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism. The questionnaire was designed by the researcher himself based on the review of the literature.

Population and sample selection

The sample of this study is a random sample. We have visited 4 mountainous tourist regions in Kosovo: Sharri Mountains, Bajgorë, Rugova Mountains and Karadak Mountains. The population of tourists per day in these regions is 100 people. The selection of the sample was done randomly.

Data collection

To identify the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism, it was necessary to create a questionnaire to obtain the necessary data. After data collection, a database was created for analysis. Due to the descriptive and predictive nature of the study, data were analyzed through the IBM SPSS statistical program, version 25.

Descriptive analysis was used to organize and summarize the data of all respondents including variables such as age, gender, school location, and others. Also, analyses were performed to assess the reliability of the questionnaires and the distribution of the questionnaires. To achieve the

objectives of the study, t-test, linear regression, and ANOVA analysis were used.

Data analysis

Once the data is prepared for analysis, researchers are open to using different methods of research and data analysis to derive more comprehensive knowledge. Of course, statistical techniques are preferred to analyze numerical data. In our study, we used:

Descriptive Statistics: These statistics are used to describe the basic features of the various types of data being researched. They present the data in such a complete way that the pattern in the data begins to make sense. However, descriptive analysis does not go beyond concluding. The conclusions are again based on the hypothesis that the researchers have formulated so far. For quantitative market research, the use of descriptive analysis often yields absolute numbers, but the analysis is never sufficient to demonstrate the reasoning behind those numbers.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

In this part of the paper, we have presented the results achieved during this research. For the most understandable and logical presentation of the results of the statistical analyses, we have presented the data in the form of tables and graphs.

Results related to demographic data

Graph 1. Gender of respondents

In graph 1, it can be seen that a total of 100 respondents participated in our study, of which 32% were female and 68% were male. Thus, the results show a dominance of the sample of male participants compared to the female one.

Graph 2. Level of education of respondents

The results show that 4% of the respondents have completed Elementary School, 32% have completed High School education, 60% have completed University Education and 4% have completed Postgraduate Education.

Table 1. Age of respondents

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	100	18.00	63.00	37.2800	13.77311
Valid N (listwise)	100				

According to the results, the lowest age of the respondents was 18 years, while the highest age was 63 years. The average age of the respondents was 37.28 years, while the standard deviation was 13.77.

Results related to descriptive data

Table 2. Descriptive data of respondents

		Never	Rarely	Average	A lot of	Highly
1	How developed is mountain tourism in Kosovo?		16%	60%	16%	8%
2	Is there enough information on social networks about mountain tourism in the Rugova region?	4%	52%	40%	4%	
3	How satisfied are you with the benefits that the electronic promotion of mountain tourism has brought you?		8%	56%	28%	8%
4	How much impact does electronic promotion have on the flow of tourists from foreign countries?			40%	28%	32%
5	Do you think that electronic promotion affects the development of mountain tourism?			20%	36%	44%
6	Do tourist agencies provide enough information about mountain			12%	68%	20%

tourism in Kosovo?						
7	Do the media (televisions, newspapers, radios) do enough marketing for mountain tourism?	20%	40%	32%	8%	
8	Does electronic promotion have an impact on the preservation of tourism potential in Kosovo?				4%	96%
9	Do you think that promotional activities through the Internet are very effective for the development of tourism?				4%	96%
10	Has electronic promotion facilitated organizational tourism?			4%	12%	84%
11	Do you think that the development of tourism affects the development of new tourist potentials?					100%
12	How satisfied are you personally with the electronic promotion of the mountain regions in Kosovo?	12%	28%	52%	8%	

13	How often have you personally visited different regions in Kosovo because of their electronic promotion?	20%	40%	32%	8%
14	Do you think that electronic promotion brings foreign investors who influence the development of tourism in Kosovo?				100%
15	Do you think it will be effective for the development of tourism to create a television channel just for the promotion of tourism in Kosovo?			8%	92%
16	Do you think that it will be effective for the development of tourism to invest in promoting tourism on the world's largest websites?				100%
17	Are you satisfied with the public investments related to the promotion of	24%	44%	28%	4%

	mountain tourism?				
18	Has mountain electronic promotion influenced environmental ethics?	8%	44%	36%	12%
19	Is there a difference between the countries of the region and Kosovo regarding the promotion of mountain tourism?	12%	56%	28%	4%
20	Can mountain tourism survive without electronic promotion?	64%	36%		

Table 3. Descriptive data related to gender differences in respondents' answers

	Age	N	Average	Standard Deviation	Average of error std
Questionnaire	Female	32	3.6625	.17180	.03037
	Male	68	3.6588	.14480	.01756

Table 4. t-test analysis regarding gender differences in respondents' answers

Questionnaire		Levent's test for equality of variance		t-test for comparison of means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	D. of averages	D. of std error	95% D. of the confidence interval	
									Low	High
Questionnaire	Estimated variances assumed	3.972	.049	.111	98	.911	.00368	.03298	-.06177	.06913
	Estimated variances not assumed			.105	52.475	.917	.00368	.03508	-.06670	.07406

From the data you have presented, it seems that there is no statistically significant difference in the answers to the questionnaire between men and women. This is evaluated by considering the significance value (p-value) found in your analysis, which is 0.91 and is greater than the significance level of 0.05. When the p-value is greater than the specified significance level (0.05 in this case), it means that there is no statistically significant difference in the averages of the questionnaire responses between men and women.

The results related to the validation of the hypotheses

In hypothesis H1, we have presented the statement that the most important Mountain Regions in Kosovo which influence the development of tourism are the Sharri Mountains and the Rugova Mountains.

Table 5. The most important mountain regions in Kosovo influence the development of tourism

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard Deviation
Sharr Mountains	25	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.78779
Rugova Mountains	25	1.00	5.00	4.5600	.80804
Bajgora Mountains	25	2.00	4.00	3.4400	.73835
Karadaku Mountains	25	1.00	5.00	3.9200	.63154

From the results, it can be observed that in the mountains of Sharri, the minimum rating of the respondents is 2, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.16 and the standard deviation is 0.78. In the mountains of Rugova, the minimum rating of the respondents is 1, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.56 and the standard deviation is 0.80. In the mountains of Bajgora, the minimum rating of the respondents is 2, the maximum is 4, the average is 3.44 and the standard deviation is 0.73. In the mountains of Karadak, the minimum rating of the respondents is 1, the maximum is 5, the average is 3.92 and the standard deviation is 0.63.

In hypothesis H2, we presented the statement that electronic promotion has a positive impact on the development of mountain tourism in the Mountain Regions of Kosovo.

Table 6. Linear regression model for the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo

Model	R	R squared	R squared adjusted	Error Estimate Std
1	.623 ^a	.389	.363	.12219

This table gives the R and R2 values. The R-value represents the simple correlation and is 0.623 ("R" column), which indicates an average correlation. The R2 value (the "R squared" column) indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable included in the model. According to this result, 62% of the variation in the

dependent variable is explained by the independent variable included in the model. In other words, 62% of the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo is explained by electronic promotion.

Table 7. ANOVA analysis for the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo

Model		Sum of squares	Df	Average squared	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.902	4	.225	15.096	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.418	95	.015		
	Total	2.320	99			

This table shows that the regression model predicts the dependent variable very well. This is observed by the "Regression" row and the "Sig" column. The p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and this indicates that the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. This indicates that the model is a good fit for the data and has statistical significance in predicting the variables of interest.

Table 8. Coefficients for the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo

Model	Unstandardized coefficients B	The std error	Standardized coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	3.189	.150		21.315	.000
The impact of electronic promotion on the flow of tourist travelers from foreign countries.	.096	.015	.534	6.249	.000
The impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism.	.035	.017	.174	2.030	.045

The impact of electronic promotion in facilitating organizational tourism.	<u>-0.018</u>	.026	<u>-0.058</u>	<u>-0.701</u>	<u>.485</u>
Visits to different regions in Kosovo as a result of electronic promotion.	.010	.014	.058	.704	.483

This table also includes Beta weights (which express the relative importance of independent variables) and collinearity statistics. The table of coefficients provides us with the information to see the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. From this table we see that the impact of electronic promotion on the flow of tourists from foreign countries has a significant result $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$), the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism has a significant result $p = 0.045$ ($p < 0.05$), while the impact of electronic promotion in facilitating organizational tourism and visits to different regions in Kosovo has a non-significant result $p = 0.48$ ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

In this chapter, the main findings of the study are summarized and a discussion of them is made in relation to the relevant literature. The findings of this study are compared with other studies by different authors, and a perspective of them is presented, which is also included in this study.

Discussions for hypothesis H1. The most important mountain regions in Kosovo that influence the development of tourism are the Sharri Mountains and the Rugova Mountains.

Tourism is a complex activity in today's modern society. The Sharri region has significant potential for public enjoyment, formal and informal tourism, as well as generating income for local businesses, the local population and local and central authorities. The region has amazing natural beauty, such as the Sharr Mountains with their wonderful landscapes, valleys, lakes, vast forests, cold springs and rivers. Vegetation is still rich and variable, and the

region has rich water resources (Avdia, 2010). In this area, different types of tourism are developed, such as mountain, winter, summer, rural tourism, outdoor activities, health tourism, mountaineering tourism, and tourist excursions. The tourist area of Sharr is of their +105 perspective, which is also included in this study.

The region of Rugova Mountains lies northwest of the city of Peja and has an area of 32,492.96 ha, in which area there are 15 villages. It is one of the mountainous regions, which includes The Cursed Mountains, with the greatest natural wealth. The beauty of this mountainous region is the Rugova Gorge, which starts only 2 km away from the city center, with a length of 12 km and then begins to open up here. The Lumbardhi River, which is formed by the sources found in different parts of Rugova, has a length of 56 km and a great velocity of water. It divides this gorge into two parts, giving it grandeur with colossal and majestic rocks, which reach heights of up to 2,000 m above sea level. The waters that spring from the rocks create waterfalls, caves, etc. In almost the entire area of Rugova Mountains, you can find miracles, hidden under the wildness of the mountain flora. Nowadays, this mountainous region has started to become very attractive for tourists and more and more residents of Kosovo and foreigners visit it, not only for walks, but also for recreational/sports activities. This region earned the name of a tourist destination by the WTTC in 2013, and visitors come specifically to visit the beauties that this mountainous region offers and to spend time in a green environment.

From the results of our study, we see that in the mountains of Sharr, the minimum rating of the respondents is 2, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.16, and the standard deviation is 0.78. In Rugova Mountains, the minimum rating of the respondents is 1, the maximum is 5, the average is 4.56, and the standard deviation is 0.80.

Discussions about the hypothesis H2. Electronic promotion has a positive impact on the development of mountain tourism in the Mountain Regions of Kosovo.

The mountains are important tourist destinations all over the world and attract visitors for their scenic beauty, sports attractions and rich cultural heritage. Tourism represents a source of income and economic opportunity for remote rural mountain communities. It can also help revitalize local traditions and food systems. However, tourism is also associated with potentially negative impacts on ecosystems, such as pollution and loss of biodiversity, as well as

on the social and cultural fabric of mountain communities. Climate change is one of the biggest challenges in mountain destinations, with impacts including a reduction in snow cover periods and an increased risk of extreme weather events. Recent years have seen an increase in the number of tourism operators using the Internet and other electronic media to carry out their marketing efforts, prioritizing electronic marketing as a new philosophy and phenomenon. In general, the number of Internet users is growing rapidly. This trend is also associated with the increase in people's confidence to do business on the Internet.

From the results of our study, we see that 62% of the development of mountain tourism in the mountain regions of Kosovo is explained by electronic promotion. The impact of electronic promotion on the flow of tourists from foreign countries has a significant result ($p = 0.000$, $p < 0.05$), while the impact of electronic promotion on the development of mountain tourism has a significant result ($p = 0.045$, $p < 0.05$). The impact of electronic promotion on facilitating the organization of tourism has a non-significant result ($p = 0.48$, $p > 0.05$), and visits to different regions in Kosovo, as a result of electronic promotion, have a non-significant result ($p = 0.48$, $p > 0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Nature-based tourism offers great development opportunities and is the second most important sector after agriculture, with an impact on development. Tourism is often considered a successful alternative to intensive agriculture, forestry, or fishing.

The post-COVID-19 era may bring new opportunities to mountain areas, as demand increases for less crowded destinations and the need to connect with open spaces and nature increases. The increase in digitization related to the COVID-19 crisis also offers the opportunity to attract remote workers and digital nomads, contributing to local development and helping to combat population decline. Specific challenges for tourism development in mountain areas include health and safety issues, as well as crisis management, as natural or man-made hazards such as floods, landslides, earthquakes, and conflicts can complicate access and services for months, or years, destroy assets, and endanger the lives of tourists.

In the development of mountain tourism, it is essential to generate income diversification and revitalize products and services, undertaking a shift from high-impact tourism activities to low-impact and climate-sensitive ones. New and innovative products have the potential to transform mountain areas into attractive tourist destinations, especially for the shoulder season. Some of the many opportunities include gastronomic tourism, community-based tourism, spiritual tourism, wellness tourism, rural tourism, agritourism, and cultural tourism.

The development of tourism and the growth of tourist capacities, especially the gathering of large numbers of people in protected nature areas, often pose a threat to sensitive ecosystems, natural habitats, plants, and animals. Therefore, it is necessary to make a detailed analysis of the impacts of tourism in these areas, as well as on the specific types of plants and animals. When evaluated from a tourism perspective, Kosovo is divided into five tourist regions: the central region of Pristina, the tourist region of the Alps Albanian, the Sharr tourist region, the Anamorava tourist region, and the Mitrovica tourist region. Based on the studies so far in the Republic of Kosovo, there are favorable conditions for the establishment of tourist centers for winter sports tourism. The tourist region of the Albanian Alps and the region of Sharri are two regions that have the greatest potential for the development of this type of tourism.

Recommendations

Some recommendations for the development of tourism in Kosovo are:

- (1) Investing more in online marketing, as this is an important trend and the most effective way to promote tourism.
- (2) To create different applications for the promotion of tourism potential in Kosovo, providing information and different offers for tourists.
- (3) To develop close cooperation between tourist agencies and municipalities to advance the development of tourism in Kosovo.
- (4) Tourist agencies should focus their offers on mountain tourism, promoting this segment and offering suitable packages and experiences for tourists.

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